

Understanding Residual Stress in Rapid-Curing Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer-Matrix Composite

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Introduction

- Excellent mechanical properties-to-density ratio of carbon fibre composites
- Achieving rapid curing cycles (higher production rates) by using new thermoset resins and moulding methods.
- Unavoidable residual stresses build up in the rapid curing process.
- Negative effects of residual stress on the fatigue properties of the ultimate product should be minimised and controlled.

This study examines the effects of processing factors on the deflection of a composite panel and proposes an efficient curing cycle.

Research Gaps and Questions

- Limited information about cure-induced shrinkage behaviour of fast cured epoxy composites compared to a conventional epoxy.
 - Lack of effective solution to reduce the cure induced residual stress.
1. Why do the internal strains increase dramatically with higher processing temperatures (120°-130°C) applied to achieve a fast cure cycle in rapid-cure epoxy systems?
 2. How can the total residual stress generated during fast-curing process be reduced?

Motivation and Project Significance

- Increasing the production rate
- Maintaining quality

Reduce the production cost in the automotive industry

Experiments and Results

Manufacturer's recommended post-curing cycle

Accurate measurement of T_{SF} during the post-curing process of partially-cured composite

Stress-Free Temperature Measurement

$$T_{SF} = \alpha \cdot T_{g_{vit}} + \frac{f(v) |\Delta V_{ChP,V}|}{CTE_{vit}} + T_{g_{avg}} \cdot (1 - \alpha_{in}) + \frac{f(v) |\Delta V_{ChP,C}|}{CTE_{F,C}}$$

Initial T_{SF} (Vitrification) Chemical shrinkage during initial curing T_g advancement during post-curing Chemical shrinkage during post-curing

Modified post-curing cycle

Equilibrating pre-cured composite at T_{SF} before post-curing resulted in lower fully-cured T_{SF}

Summary

Residual stress is one of the major hurdles for manufacturing fast cure composite parts. To understand and reduce the residual stress it is critical to identify the stress free temperature (T_{SF}) but literature is inconsistent about this. In this study:

- ✓ Stress-free temperature was successfully identified through deflection tests.
- ✓ It was proven that the measured T_{SF} was lower than the curing temperature.
- ✓ Initial experiments confirmed that the final deflection and T_{SF} can be successfully reduced by equilibrating at T_{SF} before the ultimate post-curing process.